

Adsorption of Cr^{VI} on commercially available ash powder – A kinetic approach

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Abstract : Among heavy metal pollutants, chromium plays a major role in polluting environment. Several techniques are available and among these, adsorption process is found suitable for the removal of Cr^{VI} species from wastewater. In the present work, the investigator has chosen the commercially available ash powder (CAP), which is being used as a sacred material by Hindus called "Vibhoothi or Thiruneeru" as the adsorbent. The adsorbent was characterized according to the Bureau of Indian Standards. It has also been planned to determine the adsorption potential of the adsorbent to assess the suitability of the material for the removal of Cr^{VI} from waste waters. Batch mode adsorption experiments were carried out to study the effect of initial concentration of chromium solution, effect of the dose of the adsorbent, and pH of the solution. Various models such as Lagergren, Bhattacharya and Venkobachar were tested and the results are interpreted.

Keywords : Adsorption, chromium(vi), ash powder.

The present investigation describes the mechanism of adsorption of Cr^{VI} species on to the outer surface of CAP. The study is aimed at to remove Cr^{VI} from solution of chromium by adsorption technique using the cheaply available adsorbent material in India.

Results and discussion

The physico-chemical characteristics, of the selected adsorbent, such as bulk density (0.98 g/cc), moisture content (0.607%), ash content (93.03%), matter soluble in water (1.934%), matter soluble in acid (3.26%), pH (7.2) and iron content (0.7%) were determined and are presented in the parantheses. The surface area (320.4 m²/g) was determined by BET method using nitrogen as the adsorbent at liquid nitrogen temperature. The analysis was carried out in Omnisorb 100 CX, Coulter, USA at NCL, Pune.

The pH of a wastewater is usually expected to show a profound effect on any adsorption process and in fact, it has been reported to be a significant controlling factor¹ by early workers. Cr^{VI} ions were adsorbed only at highly

acidic medium (i.e.) at the pH range of 1-2²⁻⁴. Accordingly the present study has been carried out at pH 1.5.

The experiments were conducted using a potassium dichromate solution of concentration around 10 mg dm⁻³ and the weight of the adsorbent around 0.8 g dm⁻³ at different pH values viz. 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5. The percentage of removal of Cr^{VI} and the corresponding pH are shown in the table (Table 1). The results indicate that the maximum removal of chromium occurs in the pH of around 1.0-1.5. During the process of adsorption, the

Table 1. Effect of pH on removal of chromium

Sl. no.	Solution pH	Maximum removal of Cr ^{VI} (%)
1.	0.5	58.53
2.	1.0	57.31
3.	1.5	55.48
4.	2.0	48.17
5.	2.5	48.10

rate of the removal of Cr^{VI} ions increases with increasing time, up to a certain period, and there after, the rate of removal of the solute becomes constant. At one stage, it may even become insignificant.

It is understood from the Table 2 that the residual concentration of Cr^{VI} ions in the adsorbate solution drops steeply in first 6 h, and then gradually decreases to a constant value. The initial steep drop of the residual concentration of Cr^{VI} ions is due to the rapid removal of Cr^{VI} ions which occurs as a result of the presence of large number of active adsorption sites available on the surface of the adsorbent, compared to the number of adsorbate species in the solution. Hence, for the present investigation, 7 h is presumed to represent equilibration time, which means that, 7 h appear to be sufficient for the maximum adsorption of Cr^{VI} ions by the chosen adsorbent under the given set of experimental conditions. The maximum amount of Cr^{VI} ions adsorbed corresponding to the equilibration time is found to be 48.7% for a weight of 0.4 g dm⁻³ of the adsorbent.

Table 2. Effect of contact time on removal of chromium - variation of the dose of the adsorbent

[Cr^{VI}]_{ini.}, mg dm⁻³ = 10, solution pH = 1.5, Temp., °C = 30.0 ± 1

Sl. no.	W _{adsorbent} (mg dm ⁻³)	% of removal at time <i>t</i> in hours						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	0.4	36.5	39.0	41.5	43.9	45.1	47.5	48.7
2.	0.8	39.0	42.7	47.5	48.7	51.2	52.4	54.8
3.	1.2	41.5	45.1	50.0	52.4	57.3	58.5	60.9
4.	1.6	42.7	48.8	54.8	60.9	64.6	67.1	68.3
5.	2.0	45.1	56.1	65.9	71.9	76.8	78.0	78.0

The curves drawn for the values in Table 2 are single, smooth and continuous, suggesting the probability of the formation of monolayer coverage of Cr^{VI} species on to the outer surface of the adsorbent⁵. The nature of the curves indicates that the uptake of Cr^{VI} ions per unit mass of adsorbent increases with the increasing dose of the adsorbent.

Table 2 presents the values of the amount of chromium adsorbed at the first hour as 36.5, 39.0, 41.5, 42.7 and 45%, when the concentration of the adsorbent is 0.4, 0.8, 1.2 and 2.0 g dm⁻³ respectively, and at the seventh hour the corresponding chromium removal is 48.7, 54.8, 60.9, 68.3 and 78.0%. This shows that as the dose of the adsorbent increases, adsorption of chromium also increases. The minimum time required to achieve maximum adsorption decreases for 78.0% adsorption, with

the increase of the dose of the adsorbent, which may be attributed to the increase of the surface area. In other words, the number of available active sites may be more, compared to the number of adsorbate species.

A series of isotherms were determined at five different concentrations namely 10.0, 30.0, 50.0, 70.0 and 90.0 mg dm⁻³, keeping all other experimental conditions constant, pH of the solution and temperature with a view to obtaining information about the influence of concentration on both the maximum removal of Cr^{VI} and the minimum time for maximum removal.

The values in the Table 3 indicate that the uptake of Cr^{VI} ions per unit mass of the adsorbent decreases with the increasing concentration of the solution. It is also interesting to note from the Table 3 that the amount of chromium adsorbed at the first hour is 39.0, 29.8, 22.5, 14.8 and 11.9% when the concentration of the solution is 10.0, 30.0, 50.0, 70.0 and 90.0 mg dm⁻³ respectively, and at the seventh hour, the corresponding Cr^{VI} removal is 54.8, 49.8, 42.0, 35.7 and 32.0%, which showed that as the concentration of the solution increases, adsorption of chromium decreases.

Table 3. Effect of contact time on removal of chromium - variation of the concentration of the solution

W_{adsorbent}, mg dm⁻³ = 0.8, solution pH = 1.5, Temp., °C = 30.0 ± 1

Sl. no.	W _{adsorbent} (mg dm ⁻³)	% of removal at time <i>t</i> in hours						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	8.2	39.0	42.7	47.5	48.7	51.2	52.4	54.8
2.	28.5	29.8	35.4	41.0	44.5	47.7	49.8	49.8
3.	48.0	22.5	28.8	32.7	36.0	39.3	42.0	42.0
4.	68.0	14.8	22.0	27.1	30.1	35.7	35.7	35.7
5.	88.0	11.9	21.0	26.3	30.7	32.0	32.0	32.0

The experimental data, obtained for the adsorption of Cr^{IV} on to the surface of the particles of ash powder under a given set of conditions, were analyzed in the light of the Lagergren model with a view to evaluating the mechanistic parameters associated with the process of adsorption. The Lagergren equation⁶ is

$$\log_{10} (q_e - q) = \frac{-k_{Lager}}{2.303} t + \log_{10} q_e$$

where, q_e = the amount of metal ions adsorbed at equilibrium, mg g⁻¹, q = the amount of metal ions adsorbed at time t , mg g⁻¹, k_{Lager} = the over all rate constant for the adsorption process, s⁻¹, t = time, s.

The Lagergren equation suggests linearity for the plot of $\log_{10} (q_e - q)$ against time t . From the slope of each line, the rate constants were determined. The values of $k_{\text{Lager}} \times 10^4, \text{ s}^{-1}$ obtained when different doses of the adsorbent viz. 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6 and 2.0 g dm^{-3} were used are 0.81, 0.97, 1.28, 1.39 and 1.60 s^{-1} . The results (Table 4) indicate that the rate constant increases with the increasing dose of the adsorbent.

Table 4. Effect of the dose of the adsorbent on k_{Lager} and k_{Bhatt}
 $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_{\text{ini}}, \text{ mg dm}^{-3} = 10, \text{ solution pH} = 1.5, \text{ Temp.}, ^\circ\text{C} = 30.0 \pm 1$

Sl.	Dose of the adsorbent (mg dm^{-3})	$k \times 10^4 (\text{s}^{-1})$	
no.		k_{Lager}	k_{Bhatt}
1.	0.4	0.81	0.89
2.	0.8	0.97	1.07
3.	1.2	1.28	1.28
4.	1.6	1.39	1.34
5.	2.0	1.60	1.54

Experiments were conducted with a view to examine the effect of the concentration of solution on the Lagergren rate constant. The values of $k_{\text{Lager}} \times 10^4, \text{ s}^{-1}$ obtained when different concentrations of adsorbate solution viz. 10, 30, 50, 70 and 90 mg dm^{-3} were used are 0.88, 1.09, 1.22, 1.36 and 1.49 s^{-1} respectively (Table 5). The results indicate that the rate constant increases with the increasing concentration of the adsorbate solution.

Table 5. Effect of the concentration of the solution on k_{Lager} and k_{Bhatt}
 $W_{\text{adsorbent}}, \text{ mg dm}^{-3} = 0.8, \text{ solution pH} = 1.5, \text{ Temp.}, ^\circ\text{C} = 30.0 \pm 1$

Sl.	$[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_{\text{ini}}$ (mg dm^{-3})	$k \times 10^4 (\text{s}^{-1})$	
no.		k_{Lager}	k_{Bhatt}
1.	10	0.88	1.00
2.	30	1.09	1.07
3.	50	1.22	1.22
4.	70	1.36	1.32
5.	90	1.49	1.44

The results obtained in the light of Lagergren was further confirmed by Bhattacharya and Venkobachar equation⁷

$$\log_{10} [1 - u(t)] = \frac{-k_{\text{Bhatt}}}{2.303} t$$

where,

$$u(t) = \left[\frac{C_o - C_t}{C_o - C_e} \right],$$

$k_{\text{Bhatt}} =$ over all rate constant, $\text{s}^{-1}, t =$ time, $\text{s}, C_o =$ concentration of the metal ion initially, $\text{mg dm}^{-3}, C_t =$ concentration of the metal ion at time, $t, \text{mg dm}^{-3}, C_e =$ concentration of the metal ion at equilibrium, mg dm^{-3} .

The values of $k_{\text{Bhatt}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ obtained by using different doses of the adsorbent and at under different concentration of adsorbate solution are presented in the tables (Tables 4 and 5). The k_{Bhatt} values are also similar to those of k_{Lager} .

These values reveal the trend of increasing rate constant with the increase of the dose of the adsorbent, and concentration of the solution. Further more, the applicability of the Bhattacharya and Venkobachar equation confirms the formation of monomolecular layer of Cr^{VI} species on to the surface of the adsorbent, as well as the first order kinetic nature of the process.

Experimental

The adsorbent, CAP was purchased from bulk selling merchants and stored in air tight bottles and used as such. The CAP was characterized⁸ later by the following methods suggested by Bureau of Indian Standards. A.R. Grade chemicals were used throughout. The experimental solutions were prepared by using de-ionized water.

pH measurements : The Systronics digital pH meter-335 was standardized using buffer solution. The pH of individual experimental solutions were measured by keeping the solution in a 100 ml beaker and dipping the pH electrode in the solution.

About 0.02 g of the adsorbent was accurately weighed, and transferred in to a stoppered bottle. 50 ml of the experimental chromium solution ($\cong 10 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$) was pipetted out in to the stoppered bottle containing the adsorbent, kept in a mechanical shaker and agitated for 1 h and filtered through an ordinary filter paper. The filtrate was analyzed colorimetrically for chromium. The amount of chromium adsorbed was calculated. Similarly a number of sets of experiments were conducted for 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 h to find out the equilibrium time for the adsorption of chromium on to the surface of the selected adsorbent. Batch mode experiments were conducted to study the effect of dose of the adsorbent, effect of initial concentration of chromium solution and pH of solution.

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